

Patriarchal Dominance in Animated Winning the Citra Award at the Indonesian Film Festival (FFI) 2013-2024

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Abstract

This article examines patriarchal dominance in animated works that won the Citra Award at the Indonesian Film Festival (FFI) from 2013 to 2024, through the lenses of social context, visual aesthetic development, and national identity representation. A descriptive qualitative approach is employed to analyze fourteen animated works using narrative and visual content analysis methods. The findings reveal that the themes of FFI-winning animations reflect socio-cultural issues relevant to their production periods, including social critique, gender, family values, and local mythology. Visual aesthetics evolved alongside advancements in animation technology in Indonesia, ranging from 2D techniques to complex 3D with increasingly cinematic quality. FFI jury appreciation tended to reward works that excelled technically while also incorporating national identity values through narrative, character, and cultural symbols. This includes patterns of gender representation, the roles of male and female characters, and the dominance reflected in the animations. The study's findings indicate that the majority of animated works during this period remain framed within patriarchal structures, positioning men as the center of the narrative and agency, while female characters are depicted in limited, passive, or stereotypical roles. This research contributes to animation studies by integrating analyses of social context, gender, visual aesthetics, and national identity within a single theoretical framework. It also offers recommendations for strengthening creative strategies and animation industry policies that support gender equality.

Keywords: *FFI Citra Award, Award-winning Animation, 2013–2024, Patriarchal Dominance.*

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Introduction

Indonesian animation is experiencing a significant surge in popularity. This is particularly evident since the release of *Jumbo* during the Eid holiday on March 31, 2025. By the end of July, the film had garnered over 10.171 million viewers, making *Jumbo*—produced by Visinema Studio, directed by Ryan Adriandhy, and produced by Anggia Kharisma and Novia Puspasari—the highest-grossing film in Indonesia in 2025 (Jumbo.id, 2025). It surpassed the all-time box office record previously held since 2022 by *KKN di Desa Penari* (MD Pictures), which had achieved 10,061,033 viewers in 100 days of screening. Prior to this, *Jumbo*

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had already become the highest-grossing animated film in Southeast Asia and the highest-grossing animated film ever screened in Indonesia, overtaking *Frozen 2*. (Ainaki_indonesia, 2025).

The film tells the story of three friends: Don, (Mae)saroh, and Nurman. Don is a cheerful, brave, yet sometimes stubborn boy who enjoys reading fairy tales. He is overweight, often teased as “fat,” and excluded from playing rounders with his friends because they think he is slow. However, this does not discourage Don (Jumbofilm_id, 2025). Together with Nurman and Mae, he strives to prove himself by organizing a performance based on a fairy tale book left behind by his parents. Nurman is an animal lover who keeps three goats named Mbek, Mbeek, and Mbeek, enjoys learning about various plants, is full of positive energy, easygoing yet agile, and very humorous. Mae, on the other hand, is artistically talented, creative, assertive, and deeply caring. With her Betawi accent adding a lively atmosphere, she is the type of friend who can always lighten the mood and understand others’ feelings. There is also another female character, Merry, a ghost from Germany who haunts a sugar factory where the three friends often play. (Irawanto, 2025)

In addition to these three main characters, there is an opposing figure, Atta, who always disturbs and mocks Don. Atta is characterized by his bowl-shaped haircut, independence, versatility, and skill in sports, particularly rounders. He has an older brother named Acil, who can repair radios and calm Atta when he becomes emotional. The characterization in *Jumbo* is predominantly male, with boys and men embodying masculine traits in storytelling, staging, and decision-making roles (Jumbofilm_id, 2025).

According to the official website of the Festival Film Indonesia (www.festivalfilm.id/sejarah/piala-citra), the Piala Citra was first awarded at the 1973 Festival Film Indonesia. The name was officially sanctioned by the Minister of Information of the Republic of Indonesia, Budiardjo, during the opening of the 1973 FFI in Jakarta on March 26, 1973, based on a Presidential Decree issued by President Soeharto. The intention was for the Piala Citra to become a highly respected award.

Figure 1. FFI 1955-2023 and 2013 Animation Entered the FFI Judging Category

Animation began to be included in the FFI judging categories in 2013, specifically for the “Best Short Animation” category for works under 30 minutes in duration. According to *Detik.com* (25/11/2013), Gotot Prakosa, Chair of the Jury for the Short Animated Film category, stated that there were 93 entries that year, indicating high enthusiasm among filmmakers to create animated films. By 2021, the animation category was divided into two separate awards: Best Short Animation and Best Feature Animation, the latter recognizing works longer than 70 minutes that were screened in either cinemas or on over-the-top (OTT) digital platforms. Between 2013 and 2023, twelve winners were announced—ten in the short animation category and two in the feature animation category. This development reflects the growing recognition of animation as a medium for both artistic expression and cultural storytelling. (FFI, 2021:23)

As Gotot Prakosa wrote in his book (2010:78) “Indonesian animation has developed into a medium that not only entertains but also reflects the identity and cultural values of the nation.” This statement underscores the potential of animation to serve as a contextual mirror of Indonesian society. However, as Heryanto (2014:23) observed, “Indonesian popular culture production, including animation, often faces the dilemma between meeting global market demands and the need to preserve local uniqueness.” In the context of the Piala Citra awards for animation at FFI from 2013 to 2024, it is important to examine not only aesthetic and technical achievements but also how gender representation is articulated within the medium. As Laura Mulvey (1975) has argued, visual media tend to reflect dominant social structures, including patriarchal power relations. Therefore, this study seeks to analyze how patriarchy operates in animated films deemed “the best” by FFI animation juries during this period.

Materials and Methods

This study employed a descriptive qualitative method with a narrative and visual content analysis approach. The research objects were fourteen animated films that won the Piala Citra in the Best Animation category during the 2013–2024 period. Data were obtained through direct observation of the works, documentation, and a literature review. The analytical steps included identifying the themes and social issues in each film, followed by interpreting the representation of identity through an analysis of narrative, characters, and cultural and gender symbols.

Arikunto (2022:11) asserts that “data obtained through measuring instruments, as well as the quality of data collection (tools) and the data collectors (researchers), must be clear and accurate.” Therefore, in this study, data collection was conducted systematically by the researcher. The data collection techniques used included document and object observation, interviews, documentation, and literature study.

Figure 2. Data Collection Techniques and Instruments

Another important component of the study was determining the research instruments. The primary research instrument in this study was the researcher, who gathered information from the creators of the

FFI-winning animations from 2013–2024. This process aimed to uncover phenomena, which were then formulated into research problems, supported by theoretical frameworks and research methods for analytical examination. Additional instruments included the use of structured interview guidelines. This was done to maintain the validity of the data obtained, particularly regarding how the context of Piala Citra animation winners from 2013–2023 was analyzed to derive findings from the creative process behind the animations—from pre-production, production, to post-production. Since the animation category was first introduced at the Festival Film Indonesia (FFI) in 2013, characterization trends have shown the dominance of male characters, both as protagonists and as drivers of the storyline.

Results

The analysis of Piala Citra FFI Best Animation award-winning works from 2013 to 2024 reveals consistent trends in narrative focus, character representation, and gender dynamics. Each year’s winning animation is summarized below, with an emphasis on narrative content, visual aesthetics, and representation patterns.

2013 – *Sang Suporter* (short animation category), directed by Wiryadi Dharmawan, produced by Pink Blues, Surabaya, and adapted from the comic “*Gilanya Bola*” (Cendana Art Media, 2011), <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=V42L1JT6z0s>, this 12.03-minute 2D animation—completed over a five-month production period—satirically depicts a football supporter’s rivalry to obtain a free ticket for the World Cup final in the fictional country of Balland. All key characters, both protagonist and antagonists, are male, with no significant female presence in the narrative. This composition reflects a strong patriarchal dominance (Hellofest. 2013).

2014 – *Asiaraya* (short animation category), directed by Anka Atmawijaya (Crymsonite Pictures, Jakarta), https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_SrkyZXE-1A&t=136s, this 10.16-minute hybrid 2D and 3D animation is inspired by Eiichi Hayashi’s book *Mereka yang Terlupakan: Memoar Rahmat Shigeru Ono*. The story follows a Japanese soldier, Shigeru Ono, and his Indonesian driver, Yusuf, during the Japanese surrender in World War II and their efforts to assist Indonesia’s independence movement. All central figures are male, reinforcing the patriarchal pattern.

Figure 3. Animation of the Winners of the 2013-2023 FFI Citra Award

2015 – *GWK* (short animation category), directed by Chandra Endroputro, produced by GWK Cultural Park and Alam Sutera Property, with 3D animation by Infinite Frame Work Batam, this 30-minute work narrates a Balinese myth about young Garuda's quest to retrieve the *tirta amerta* (water of life) from Lord Vishnu to free his mother, Dewi Winata, from the witch Kadru. Although female characters appear as the mother (victim) and antagonist, narrative control remains with little Garuda and Vishnu, reflecting a patriarchal narrative structure.

2016 – *Surat untuk Jakarta* (short animation category), Directed by Andre Sugianto and colleagues (Pijaru Kompas Gramedia), this 2.06-minute 2D motion graphics piece portrays Jakarta's bustling life without dialogue or visible character identities. However, the silhouettes predominantly depict men—motorbike riders, truck drivers, and workers—symbolizing male dominance in public spaces.

2017 – *Lukisan Nafas* (short animation category), Directed by Fajar Ramayel (Dawn Animation), <https://youtu.be/k0vu6fkJt1Q> this 12-minute 3D animation tells the story of Nina, a young girl who continues her father's mission to photograph rare birds after he is injured. Although the story begins with the father leading the narrative, it concludes with Nina taking an independent role, providing a stronger female representation compared to previous years.

2018 – *Si Juki the Movie* (feature film animation with single category), Directed by Faza "Meonk" Ubaidillah-Pionicon agency and Daryl Wilson-Kumata Studio for animation director collaboration with Falcon Pictures), this 97-minute 2D animated feature adapts the popular *Si Juki* comic to the movie, now still showing in over the top digital platform; Netflix. The story dominance on Juki and his predominantly male associates, with Erin, a female scientist, and Juki's mother as supporting figures. Despite the presence of female production staff (e.g., executive producer Frederica), on-screen dominance remains with male characters.

2019 – *Nussa Bisa* (short animation category), directed by Bony Wirasmono (*The Little Giantz* in collaboration with 4 Stripe Production), still showing in youtube channel, NussaOfficial: <https://youtu.be/-5LNffQwITE>, this 11.33-minute story follows Nussa, a boy with a disability, determined to play soccer despite his mother's prohibition. His younger sister Rara provides emotional support. While more female characters appear, the story focuses on Nussa's journey, with the final decision controlled by the mother figure.

2020 – *Prognosis* (short movie animation category), directed by Ryan Adriandhy (Rochester Institute of Technology), <https://youtu.be/A22WadH-cJc?si=d4LJxJ0ABO-bshiZ>, this 10-minute animation portrays the strained relationship between a father and his son after the mother's passed away A found robot becomes a catalyst for emotional reconciliation. The conflict and resolution revolve entirely around male characters, maintaining male-centered narrative control.

2021 – *Nussa the Movie* (feature film animation category) and *Ahasveros* (short movie animation category), *Nussa the Movie*, a 107-minute 3D animated feature directed by Bony Wirasmono (*The Little Giantz* & Visinema), centers on a rivalry between Nussa and newcomer Jonni in a science competition. The narrative, conflict, and resolution are dominated by these two male characters, with female characters present mainly in family settings. Now *Nussa the Movie* still showing in over the top platform, Prime video Amazon. *Ahasveros*, directed by Bobby Fernando (UMN Pictures) with the producer: Kemal Hasan, Salima Hakim, and Yohanes Merci, is a short noir animation portraying the existential anxiety of poet Chairil Anwar. The narrative focuses entirely on a masculine historical-literary figure.

2022 – *Blackout* (short animation category), Directed by Faiz Azhar (UMN), still can access in youtube channel Faiz Azhar: <https://youtu.be/W-F3sQe8wN4>, this 4.54-minute animation tells of a young man trapped in virtual reality until a blackout forces the ecosystem and then to be able reconnect in the physical world. A critique of technological dependency in an increasingly digitalized Indonesia, "Blackout" reminds us that human reality—social interaction, natural beauty, and feelings—cannot be completely replaced by the metaverse. This animated moment aired during a period of post-pandemic social isolation, this animation emerged after the covid-19 pandemic era accelerated the use of remote technology, so the story relates to the conditions of that time 2021, that heavily utilized digital space. To

the point of blackouts as a social phenomenon that may not be unfamiliar in many parts of Indonesia. The Blackout animation serves as a metaphor for the fragility of cyberspace and the importance of returning to reality. The story remains framed from a male protagonist's perspective.

2023 – *Trung Tung* (short movie animation category), Directed by Bony Wirasmono and Aditya Triantoro (*The Little Giantz Studio*), from the youtube channel LittleGiantz: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=azwk8ScfOXk&t=44s_this 12-minute animation personifies a male-gendered pickup truck as the main character, the pickup truck name is Trung Tung. Supporting roles—police officers and mechanics—are also male, with female presence limited to a brief appearance. The animation's core themes are the internal journey of overcoming breakout past trauma when his father crashing with locomotive in the track of train, the power of healing with a tight-knit friendship like family, and the (“mudik”) homecoming tradition which describes the story and fuels the main character Trungtung's inner conflict.

2024 – *Si Juki the Movie: Harta Pulau Monyet* (feature film animation category) and ***Cangkir Profesor*** (short animation category), In *Si Juki the Movie: Harta Pulau Monyet* (directed by Faza Meonk and Daryl Wilson, collaboration with Falcon Pictures), this 97-minute 2D animated feature, Juki embarks on a treasure-hunting adventure to monkeys island with his male companions. Female characters such as Susi and Juki's mother play supporting roles. *Cangkir Profesor*, from youtube channel Manimonki studio: <https://youtu.be/etM9fKSDB84?si=Db6QkPaOxVbT32BY>, this 11-minute animation, (adapted from the *Pupus* webtoon by Kurnia Harta Winata, directed by Yudhatama, Manimonki Studio, Solo) features a teenage girl, Pupus, as the main character. However, narrative authority rests with Professor Surya, a male figure, maintaining male decision-making dominance.

Hegemony of Masculinity

Aryo Damartoto (2010) adds that masculinity is a cultural construction; men are not born with masculine traits but are shaped by cultural norms. Traditional masculinity prioritizes values such as strength, power, and control while undervaluing interpersonal relationships and domestic life (Panuju, 2021: 118).

Laura Mulvey (1975) concept of the male gaze explains how mainstream cinema constructs narratives from the perspective of the heterosexual male viewer, positioning women as objects of visual pleasure rather than active subjects. This theoretical lens clarifies why female characters in the analyzed animations often function to support the male protagonist's journey rather than pursue their own narrative arcs, as seen in films like *GWK*, *Nussa Bisa*, *Si Juki the Movies*, *Lukisan Nafas*, and *Cangkir Profesor*.

Feminist theory emphasizes that the representation of women in media is never neutral. As described by Liesbet van Zoonen (1994), women are frequently constructed in subordinate positions through narratives controlled by patriarchal logic. The discourse on masculinity is inherently tied to the discussion of gender. R.W. Connell's (1995) concept of hegemonic masculinity defines it as the culturally and socially legitimized dominant form of masculinity. In animation, this manifests in protagonists characterized as heroic, rational, and active—traits typically associated with men in a patriarchal system.

Patriarchy is also visible in the animation production structure. The majority of directors, screenwriters, and producers of these animations creators are men, reinforcing bell hooks' (1984) observation that patriarchal domination is embedded not only in representation but also in the control over narrative creation. The animation ecosystem context suggests that the gender imbalance behind the scenes correlates with the persistence of male-centered narratives on screen.

Table 1. Creators and Judges of the FFI 2013-2024 FFI Animation Categories

No.	Research Object	Director/Creator	Jury
1.	Sang Suporter (2013)	Sutradara: Wiryadi Dharmawan, Studio Pink Blues, Surabaya	Dermawan Syamsudin, Bambang Gunawan Santoso, Adi Nugroho,

			Rachmat Rizal, Gotot Prakosa (alm)
2.	Asia Raya (2014)	Sutradara: Anka Atmawijaya Studio: Crymsonite Pictures, Bekasi	Gotot Prakosa (alm), Dana Riza, Chandra Endroputro Wiryadi Dharmawan
3.	GWK (2015)	Sutradara: Chandra Endroputro Studio: GWK Cultural Park & Alam Sutera Property, Tangerang Selatan	Achmad Rofiq, Chandra Endroputro, Fredy Nindan, Marsha Chikita Fawzi, Firman Widyasmara Anka Atmawijaya
4.	Surat Untuk Jakarta (2016)	Sutradara: Aditya Prabaswara Studio: Pijaru KG Production, Jakarta	Aryanto Yuniawan, Amien Wibawa, Indra Jaya
5.	Lukisan Nafas (2017)	Sutradara: Fajar Ramayel Studio: Dawn Animation, Jakarta	Chandra Endroputro, Wahyu Aditya, Aditya Prabaswara
6.	Si Juki the movie: Panitia Hari Akhir (2018)	Sutradara: Faza Meonk, Daryl Wilson, Produksi: Pionicon, Falcon Pictures, Kumata studio, Jakarta	Wiryadi Dharmawan (Bali), Fajar Ramayel, Wahyu Aditya
7.	Nussa Bisa (2019)	Sutradara: Bony Wirasmono Aditya Triantoro Studio: Studio the Little Giantz, Visinema, Jakarta	Chandra Endroputro, Wahyu Aditya, Faza Meonk, Aditya Prabaswara
8.	Prognosis (2020)	Sutradara: Ryan Adriandhy Studio: Visinema Pictures, Jakarta	Chandra Endroputro, Wahyu Aditya, Bony Wirasmono
9.	Ahasveros (2021) Nussa the Movie: Panitia Hari Akhir (2021)	Produser: Kemal Hasan Studio: UMN Pictures, Tangerang Selatan Sutradara: Bony Wirasmono Aditya Triantoro Studio: Studio the Little Giantz, Visinema, Jakarta	Juri awal: Aryanto Yuniawan, Ellen Xie, Daryl Wilson Juri akhir: Chandra Endroputro, Wahyu Aditya, Ryan Adriandhy
10.	Blackout (2022)	Produser: Faiz Azhar Studio: UMN, Tangerang Selatan	Juri awal: Dermawan Syamsuddin, Ehwan Kurniawan, Yudhatama, Juri akhir: Chandra Endroputro, Kemal Hasan, Bony Wirasmono
11.	Trungtung (2023)	Sutradara: Bony Wirasmono Studio: Studio the Little Giantz, Visinema, Jakarta	Juri awal: M. Rifan, Cahya Daulay, Eka Chandra. Juri akhir: Daryl Wilson, Dana Riza, Aditya Triantoro
12.	Si Juki the movie: Harta Pulau Monyet (2024) Cangkir Profesor (2024)	Sutradara: Faza Meonk, Daryl Wilson Sutradara: Yudhatama, Kurnia Harta	Juri awal: Roy, Johannes Kurnia, Andi Wijaya Juri akhir: Bony Wirasmono, Chandra Endroputro, Ronny Gani

Conclusion

The data from the winning animations category of the Indonesian Film Festival (FFI) from 2013–2024 reveal a consistent pattern: male protagonists dominate the central narrative focus. From *Sang Suporter* (2013), *Asia Raya* (2014), *GWK* (2015), *Surat Untuk Jakarta* (2016), *Lukisan Nafas* (2017), *Si Juki the movie: Panitia hari akhir* (2018), *Nussa Bisa* (2019), *Prognosis* (2020), *Nussa the movie* and *Ahasveros* (2021), *Blackout* (2022), *Trungtung* (2023) until to *Si Juki the Movie: Harta Pulau Monyet* (2024), the main character, heroic, active, and leadership roles are overwhelmingly occupied by men. Female characters, in contrast, are primarily placed in supporting or stereotypical roles: as victims (little Garuda's mother in *GWK*), or villains (the witch Kadru in *GWK*), passive decision-makers (Umma in *Nussa Bisa*), or emotional stabilizers (Erin in *Si Juki the Movie*; Rara in *Nussa*).

Even when female characters appear in leading positions—as with Nina in *Lukisan Nafas* (2017)—their narrative agents often remains framed within the legacy of a male figure. The scarcity of feminine

perspectives underscores the male-dominated narrative structure of Indonesia's animation ecosystem. The focus on male struggles and heroism reinforces a masculine narrative bias, positioning men as both agents of change and the primary objects of audience identification. Not only in the creators of the 2013-2024 Citra Award animation winners, male dominance was also seen in the jury who judged the FFI animation category from 2013-2024 (attached in Table 1).

Beyond on-animation movie, patriarchal dominance is also reflected in the continuity of male creators. Most directors, writers, and producers are men, illustrating a lack of female involvement in core creative roles. A few exceptions exist—such as Frederica as executive for *Si Juki the Movie* (2018) and Anggia Kharisma and Widya Arifianti as writers for *Nussa the Movie* (2021)—but these remain limited.

The unprecedented success of *Jumbo* (2025), characterized by its exceptional quality and positive audience reception, may serve as a catalyst for greater inclusion of talented women at all stages of animation production. Such inclusion is essential not only for gender equity but also for expanding the diversity of narratives and perspectives in Indonesian animation. May Indonesian animation continue to move forward.

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